

STUDY OF CHANNEL MODEL FOR WIRELESS COCKPIT DISPLAY SYSTEM FOR MILITARY TRANSPORT AIRCRAFT

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ABSTRACT

Issues of increased weight, Electro-Magnetic Interference (EMI), installation, maintenance, upgradation of legacy systems, modifications and increased risk of fire due to arcing and shorting of onboard cables in aircraft has resulted in wireless networks gradually gaining relevance for future generation aircraft. Wireless technology can meet most of the challenges of modern avionics systems, apart from significantly reducing the weight due to wires and associated hardware, with proper selection of technology. Wireless technology is already in use for in-flight entertainment systems. Wireless Avionics Intra Communication (WAIC) is expected to pave the way for use of wireless technology in avionics. One of the crucial factors in introducing a wireless network in an aircraft is to identify the channel model inside an aircraft. This paper aims to study various channel models, including the one recommended by International Telecommunication Union (ITU), for analysing the channel for the cockpit display system inside a military transport aircraft. Based on the analysis and simulation results, the likely channel has been identified.

Keywords: Channel, WAIC, transport, Display, Wireless

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Nomenclature

P_t	Transmit power (watts)
P_r	Received Power (watts)
λ	Wavelength of radiation (m)
L	Channel gain/loss (dB)
G_t	Gain of transmit antenna
G_r	Gain of receive antenna
$P_r(d)$	Received power at distance d
$PL_F(d)$	Free-space path loss at distance d
$PL_{LD}(d)$	Log Normal Path loss at distance d
$PL_F(d_0)$	Free-space path loss at a reference distance d_0
X_σ	Zero-mean Gaussian distributed random variable, with standard deviation σ (dB)
$h(f,d)$	Large scale channel gain/loss model (dB)
Y	Model prediction error in $h(f,d)$ due to shadowing effects
X	Small scale channel gain/loss model (dB)
C_1	Constant offset (dB)
n	Distance exponent (m)
f	Frequency component (Hz)

1. Information

A avionics in aircraft has been growing at a fast pace, with an aim to cater for the ever increasing demand for real-time data at a faster rate. Real-time information about on-board system status, warnings or information etc. is provided to the aircrew by a highly reliable, efficient and secured data network. Military transport aircraft includes A321, C-130, C-17, B737-400, B737-200, A340-300, CRJ700, DC-10 etc, which are used for transportation of men and material, for Airborne Early Warning task, as Airborne Warning and Control System

(AWACS) platform etc. The specific usage of these aircraft for military purposes is tabulated later in the paper. The paper thus focuses on these platforms for developing the channel model.

Data networks in all military aircraft both transport and fighters are presently built upon physical connections using wires which follow data bus standards like MIL-STD-1553, ARINC 429, ARINC 629, ARINC 664/AFDX etc. These networks result in large quantity of onboard cables. Length of on-board cables in Boeing 747 to the 777-300 varies from 110 miles to 150 miles (Slutsken, Apr 2017) and the A380-800 carries cables equal to 290 miles (AVSI, 2015). On-board wires in an aircraft have been a major cause of concern for the aircraft manufacturers and operators primarily due to the additional weight of the wires. Issues faced by US Navy over the years, with respect to aircraft wiring has been discussed in (Collins, 2006). In order to address the problems due to electrical wiring, a team of skilled engineers, technicians, logisticians, and uniformed service members was assembled. Three critical areas identified by the team were wiring components, designs and installations, and maintenance and training. The paper focuses on the problems related to each of the three identified critical areas. In an article, which appeared in Aviation News (Flight Safety Foundation Editorial Staff, 2005), four separate incidents caused due to aircraft wiring have been brought out. The incidents due to abrasion and arcing in wires occurred in different systems at different locations. These incidents caused damage to the wires and resulted in short circuit of wires, causing smoke/fire inside the aircraft. The report on possible cause of the Trans World Airlines (TWA) Flight 800 Boeing 747-131 crash (National Transportation Safety Board, 2023) has clearly brought out that the separation of wires, mentioned in the relevant standards, was not sufficient to provide protection against short circuits inside the aircraft. A short circuit near the central fuel tank ignited the fuel vapours inside the tank causing a mid-air explosion. Similarly, the cause of the crash of Swissair flight 111, McDonnell Douglas MD-11, was attributed to arcing in the power supply cable of the In-Flight Entertainment Network (IFEN) (McDonnell Douglas MD-11 HB-IWF, Sep 1998). The arcing caused a fire in that area and since no smoke or fire detection system was available in that area, the fire spread to other areas and became uncontrollable. In (Peng & Chao, 2011), the issue of EMI, due to electromagnetic coupling caused by improper wiring, in aircraft Electrical Wiring Interconnect System (EWIS) has been discussed. This in turn reduces the amount of fuel and payload that can be carried onboard. In addition, sufficiently large amount of maintenance effort is involved in rectifying cable faults. These aspects have a direct bearing on the manufacturing and operations cost. In US Navy's SH 60 (Sea Hawk) helicopter a weight reduction of 120 Kg is feasible by reducing the cables by 50% [3]. In Airbus 380-800, 30% of the onboard cables onboard can be replaced with wireless network (AVSI, 2015). In Cessna

310R, a weight reduction of 40 Kg, will result in a range increase by 10% [3]. Aircraft manufacturers are looking at options to reduce weight. One option was the use of optical cables, as done in F-22 (Brower, 2000) and F-35 and another was the use of wireless communication. The most significant work in the field of using wireless technology for internal aircraft communication, for flight critical systems, is being carried out under the Wireless Avionics Intra Communication (WAIC) program. The major partners in the program, under AVSI, are Airbus, Embraer, Honeywell, Lufthansa Technik, NASA, Rockwell Collins, Thales, United Technologies, and Zodiac Inflight Innovations. The members are confident that in the next five years, required technical knowhow would be available for integrating wireless based systems in an aircraft. WAIC by Aerospace Vehicle System Institute (AVSI), with participation of leading aircraft manufacturers aims to integrate the on-board LRUs through a wireless network (AVSI, 2015). WAIC program deals only with wireless communication between two or more points in an aircraft for flight critical systems. It does not cater for air-to-ground, air-to-satellite, or air-to-air service and also does not include passenger communications and in-flight entertainment. On, 27 Nov 2015, ITU concluded their deliberations at the World Radio communication Conference and granted 4.2 – 4.4 GHz frequency band for WAIC systems “to allow for the heavy and expensive wiring used in aircraft to be replaced by wireless systems”.

Introducing wireless applications for intra communication is likely to result in interference with other onboard systems operating in the same band. This interference can be between WAIC systems with systems of same aircraft or onboard other aircraft and also between WAIC systems and ground systems. For onboard systems, the maximum interference is likely to be from Radio Altimeter (RA), since RA also operates in 4.2-4.4 GHz band. Technical characteristics and protection criteria for RA is given in ITU report (International Telecommunication Union, Feb. 2014) and forms the basis for interference analysis. In addition, the band of 4.2 – 4.4 GHz may be used by Earth Exploration-Satellite Service (EESS), Space Research Service (SRS) and Fixed Service (FS) on a secondary basis (International Telecommunication Union, Nov. 2014), (Suryanegara, Nashirudin, Raharya, & Asvial, Dec. 2015). Interference analysis of RA on WAIC systems onboard the same aircraft ((Hanschke, Kruger, Meyerhoff, Renner, & Timm-Giel, May 2017), (Meyerhoff, Farber, & Schwark, Feb. 2015), (Futatumori, et al., 2018), (Engelbrecht, Fuss, Schwark, & Michler, Nov. 2014)), between WAIC aircraft and RA aircraft in flight and WAIC aircraft on ground and RA aircraft in landing phase [31], multiple WAIC aircraft on ground (International Telecommunication Union, Dec. 2013) has been carried out. ITU, based on analysis, has recommended that

directional antenna with reduced power and separation of 150 m is sufficient to prevent interference between WAIC and RA.

In any wireless communication system, all the changes that take place in a signal happens in the medium through which the signal passes. Thus, knowledge of the channel through which the signal is expected to pass is of great importance. The channel models help in estimating the signal strength at the receiver. The accuracy of the predicted model is important to analyse the propagation of the signal through the channel. This paper aims to look at a channel model for wireless Flight Deck display system, which includes the path from the sensors to the Multi-Functional Displays (MFD) in the cockpit.

A typical Flight Deck display system architecture for a military aircraft is shown in Fig. 1. The architecture would be simpler for commercial aircraft, with reduced sensors, due to non-availability of Weapons, Fire Control Radar etc. Though the number of similar types of sensors may increase due to the size of the aircraft. However, while considering the channel model, commercial aircraft also have been considered. The sensors are embedded in systems like flight control systems, engine, fuel system, Environment Control System (ECS) system, smoke sensors etc.

Fig. 1 Architecture of a typical Flight Deck Display System in a military aircraft

The data from the sensors are processed by the individual system computers before forwarding it to data concentrators. The system computers usually act as data concentrators and will be different for different groups of sensors. Data Concentrator Unit accumulates data from

the sensors. The received data is converted into the required format for use by other aircraft systems. The data concentrator considered in Fig.1 is the Payload Management Unit (PMU). Apart from the data available from the sensors, the unit would also receive videos/images from sensors. The data is then forwarded to the Avionics Computer/Mission Computer/ Core Integrated Processor/Integrated Aircraft Computer(IAC), which is the heart of the avionics system. The data from the IAC is then sent to the Display Control Module. The Display Control Module is the main LRU of the display system. Though the system is controlled by IAC, Display Control Module controls the information displayed in the cockpit MFDs.

The channel inside an aircraft is expected to be different from the channel encountered in a land based wireless communication system, due to the presence of large amount of on-board metallic structures, absorbent materials, composites etc. Due to the limitation of carrying out measurements inside an aircraft, the channel model in the present research has been derived based on the studies carried out inside different aircraft, including the proposed model by ITU brought out in (International Telecommunication Union, 2014).

II. Channel Model

The channel inside an aircraft for wireless communication needs to be modelled by considering the location of the LRU, metallic obstructions, passenger movement (inside cabin) etc. The noise in a channel may be due to natural causes like lightning, which is a source for impulse types of noise, or it may be due to those produced by humans. The noises may be due to generators, ignition in aircraft or radio transmissions etc. The continuous break and make contact of the brushes and in turn the commutator with the rotating armature of generator create an impulse type of noise. Similarly, the ignition plugs in aircraft engines create regular sparks which also are impulse noises. The radio communications taking place in an aircraft are also sources of radio interference. In the subsequent paragraphs various standard channel models, their applicability in an aircraft and means of estimating the channels are brought out.

A. Propagation Models

Propagation of radio signals in wireless communications systems is modelled separately for indoor and outdoor environment. For aircraft intra communication, indoor propagation models are more relevant. Though, one may have to consider the outdoor propagation model for communication between sensors mounted on the wings or from the engine to fuselage compartment, the paper focuses on indoor channel models in an aircraft.

Several outdoor propagation models are available to predict path loss (Rappaport, 1996), (Barsocchi, 2006), (Cho, Kim, Yang, & Kang, 2010). The most common models include Longley-Rice model, Okumura/Hata Model, Walfisch and Bertoni Model and IEEE 802.16d Model. The indoor channel is usually considered to be static or quasi-static. The static condition is when the degree of variation of the signal with respect to symbol duration is relatively small. In an aircraft scenario, the channel for intra communication can also be considered as static or quasi-static. A quasi-static model may be considered inside cabin and cockpit because of movement of passengers or crew. However inside equipment compartments, the channel may be considered to be static because there are no movements. There are a large number of indoor channel models. The most prominent and popular among these are the 2-ray model, exponential model, Saleh-Valenzuela (S-V) model, ray tracing model and UWB channel model. In addition, there are other channel models like the one defined by Joint Standards Committee (JTC), for three different scenarios residential, office and commercial areas. Due to the tube shape of the aircraft fuselage, multiple reflections of the signal are available. No specific statistical channel model for cabin communications have been identified, though researchers have presented different models which are discussed in the latter part. ITU has recommended a statistical model in (International Telecommunication Union, 2014) for WAIC. In order to establish a statistical model, a large amount of channel measurement data is required, which is costly, time-consuming and difficult to carry out due to restrictions of certifying agencies and the manufactures of the aircraft.

The European Aeronautic Defence and Space Company (EADS) Innovation Works (Piche, Urrea, & Peres, 8-12 April 2013) has presented a channel model by simulating a complex avionic environment. The study focuses on theoretical backgrounds of channel models. A numerical approach to deal with highly resonant structures is presented in the study report. EADS frequency domain software ASERIS BE which solves the Electric Field Integral Equation (EFIE) with a Boundary Element Method (BEM) has been used for the numerical approach. The concept is used to determine the channel model for the cabin of Airbus A320. To carry out measurements, an omni directional transmitting and receiving antenna were mounted on a precision motorized rail (1m long). Two different configurations, with antenna in LOS, were tested by the team. A statistical variation following Rice law (presence of a dominant path due to LOS and multipath) has been used.

Measurement of broadband indoor channels have indicated that multipath fading follows the log-normal or Nakagami distribution rather than the Rayleigh distribution, even if they show the same phenomenon of clustering as in the Saleh-Valenzuela (S-V) channel model

(Saleh & Valenzuela, February 1987). Based on these results, UWB multipath models have been proposed for indoor wireless propagation. The use of UWB communication system has been extended beyond indoor environments to aircraft. Due to the high data rate, aircraft manufacturers are interested in setting up UWB channel inside aircraft for high data rate applications, like on demand video for in-flight entertainment. Statistical models for UWB indoor channel have been developed by many researchers. In (Chuang J. , Xin, Huang, Chiu, & Michelson, Apr 2007) study on UWB radio propagation in Boeing 737-200 aircraft has been carried out. It focuses on actual measurements inside the passenger cabin in the 3-10.6 GHz band. Data collection was carried out in a point-to-multipoint configuration. A bi-conical UWB transmitting antenna was mounted at three locations in the cabin ceiling and identical receiving antenna were mounted at headrest, armrest, and footrest level at over 50 locations throughout the cabin. The measurements have shown that human presence and location of receiving antenna affects UWB propagation inside the aircraft. In (Saghir, Nerguizian, Laurin, & Moupfouma, Jan. 2014), the authors have carried out measurements inside a Bombardier's commercial regional jet aircraft CRJ 700. It assumes a channel inside the aircraft and measurements were made to model both small scale and large scale models. For large scale measurements two Rx and Tx antenna positions were considered and for small scale measurements the Tx antenna was placed at the beginning of the passengers' aisle and Rx antenna was moved in a grid at 63 points. Measurements were made at 2.45 GHz and 5.8 GHz. The value of path loss exponent n for LOS was found to be <2 The mean path loss at 5.8 GHz was found to be 10 dB higher than at 2.45 GHz. The Root Mean Square (RMS) delay spread at 2.45 GHz is found to be 50nS and at 5.8 GHz to be 33nS, similar to values obtained for indoor propagations. For small scale multipath fading the Rice model is considered more representative with K value of 8.5 dB at 2.45 GHz and 11 dB at 5.8 GHz. Measurements inside a C-130 aircraft (military cargo aircraft), in UWB band, for path loss exponent and time dispersion parameters is given in (Spiliotopoulos & Kanatas, 2010). The measurements were carried out at 13 different locations under LOS (cargo cabin) and NLOS (between crew and cargo cabin) conditions. The channel transfer function has been calculated by keeping the transmitter fixed and placing the receiver at different positions. The path loss factor n for frequency bandwidth of 0.75 GHz up to 7.5 GHz has been presented in the paper. Based on the measured value of n the path loss model has been validated by calculating the error between the estimated path gain model and measured path gain. The mean value of the error was found to vary between -0.23 dB and -3.03 dB. In (Zhang & Yu, 2011), real-time aircraft cabin channel model is established with ray-tracing algorithm. In the simulation an access point(AP) is

deployed in the middle part of the cabin. The resultant data is used to establish a statistical channel model in the aircraft cabin. The channel proposed is of the form of Nakagami channel because it combines the properties of Rayleigh and Rice fading. A 3D ray-tracing model of the deck of a wide-bodied aircraft has been presented in (Felbecker, Keusgen, & Peter, 2008). The system utilizes the 60 GHz frequency band with a signal bandwidth of 250 MHz per frequency channel. 3D model of a deck including seats and passengers has been drawn up for the simulations. Simulations have shown that SNR strongly depends on the presence of passengers and is around 21 dB for the non-occupied scenario and around 19 dB in the fully occupied scenario. 3-D model of an aircraft cabin and ray tracing. In (Mankowski, Vijayaraghavan, Hilla, & Kellerer, 2024) also a 3-D model based on a Boeing 737–400 aircraft has been developed, with realistic electrical properties for the components of the cabin, using ray tracing. Different channel properties for receiver positions along the aisle and the seat screens and in front of the passengers by processing have been obtained. The authors have presented a Path Loss model, Tapped Delay line model and Clustered Delay line model for the cabin in the for 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz.

B. Propagation Effect

In a large scale model, the path loss is given by the Friis Equation and expressed as a function of distance d between the transmitter and receiver (equation (1)). With antenna gains $G_t = G_r = 1$

$$PL_F(d)[\text{dB}] = 10 \log\left(\frac{P_t}{P_r}\right) = 20 \log\left(\frac{4\pi d}{\lambda}\right) \quad (1)$$

A more generalised path loss is given equation (2) and is proportional to the distance d , relative to a reference distance d_0 , risen to the power n (International Telecommunication Union, 2014).

$$PL(d)[\text{dB}] = PL_F(d_0) + 10n \log\frac{d}{d_0} \quad (2)$$

It is evident that with an increase in value of n , the path loss increases, even with no variation in the distance d between the transmitter and receiver. The increase in path loss is due to the variation in the surrounding environment

Measurements have been carried out inside multiple aircraft to find the value of n inside an aircraft. The value of n is found to vary in different conditions of LOS and NLOS. For

narrower aircraft like CRJ700, the value was found to be 0.35-2, which is lower than the free space value of 2. For C-130 aircraft also, the value is found to be below 2. For wide bodied aircraft like A321 value of n was found to be greater than 2. The reason is likely due to narrow width of the CRJ700 fuselage. The measurements indicate that inside an aircraft, the propagation conditions are likely to be better due to the guiding/tunnelling effect of the fuselage and the losses are therefore reduced in a narrow-bodied aircraft. In case of NLOS condition the values of n are found to be above 2, due to obstructions in direct path. The value of n is found to increase with increasing distance between transmitter and receiver. The value of n , recommended by ITU based on measurements inside a DC-10 aircraft, is equal to the free space value of 2 (International Telecommunication Union, 2014). The values of n obtained for different aircraft, along with their military usage, is tabulated below in Table 1 (Piche, Urrea, & Peres, 8-12 April 2013), (Cogalan, Videv, & Haas, 2017), (Jemai, et al., 10-12 Sept. 2008), (Chuang J. , Xin, Huang, Chiu, & Michelson, 29 May 2007), (Saghir, Nerguizian, Laurin, & Moupfouma, Jan. 2014), (Spiliotopoulos & Kanatas, 2010), (Moraitis & Constantinou, 2008).

Table 1 Path Loss Exponent in Aircraft

Aircraft	Military Usage	Path Loss Exponent (n)
A321	AWACS, India (Under Development)	1.5-2.6
C-130	Military Transport	0.2-1.54
B737-400]	Used as AEW&C by Australian, Turkish, Korean, UK and US Air Forces	2.1-2.3
B737-200]		1.16-1.23
A340-300	German Air Force as VIP aircraft	2-2.7
CRJ700	China's People's Liberation Army Air Force and Naval Air Force. Similar to ERJ 145 used as AEW&C by India, Mexican and Greek Air Forces	0.35-2
DC-10	Military version is KC-10, Aerial Refueller	2

While equation (2) does take into effect the surrounding environment, the shadowing effect of objects in the path of the signal is not considered. Moreover, equation (2) only takes the average and therefore is not a correct representation of the signal path. The environment of different locations of transmitters and receivers may be quite different, even though the separating distances may be similar. These variations, at times, are found to be large. For a given value of d , the path loss $PL(d)$, is found to be random and with log-normal distribution, about the mean distance. In order to study the effect of shadowing, measurements were carried out, inside an Airbus A319 cabin (Jemai, et al., 10-12 Sept. 2008) in the frequency range 3-8 GHz, by positioning the transmitter at three locations in the upper part of the side wall. For

these three transmitter locations, different receiver positions were distributed at head rest and arm rest. The measured data were used to calculate path loss model parameters for LOS and NLOS. The empirical formula is slightly different from the Log Distance path loss model at distance d for a reference d_0 and is independent of the frequency and is given by equation (3).

$$PL_{LD}(d)[\text{dB}] = PL_F(d_0) + 10n \log \frac{d}{d_0} + X_\sigma(\text{dB}) \quad (3)$$

C. Small Scale Fading

Small-scale fading, as discussed earlier, is used to describe the rapid fluctuation of the amplitude of a radio signal over a short period of time or travel distance, so that large-scale path loss effects may be ignored. Small scale fading is caused mainly due to multipath in the radio channel (Rappaport, 1996), (Barsocchi, 2006). It also causes echoes due to multipath propagation delays of the signal and random frequency modulation due to Doppler shifts. The factors which affect small scale fading are:

1. *Multipath Propagation*

Any channel contains reflecting objects and scatters. These objects dissipate the signal energy in amplitude, phase, and time. Due to dissipation of the signal energy multiple versions of the transmitted signal arrive at the receiver. The arrival of the signals is separated from one another in time and spatial orientation. The random variation in phase and amplitudes of the received signals causes variation in signal strength. These random fluctuations result in small-scale fading, signal distortion, or both. Multipath will be a cause of major concern in an aircraft environment with multiple LRUs and metallic structures available in the close vicinity of the transmitter.

2. *Speed of the mobile and surrounding objects*

Another factor resulting in small scale fading is the relative motion between the base station and the mobile and the movement of the objects around the mobile station. If the mobile stations are in motion, they induce a Doppler shift on the multipath components and cause frequency modulation of each of the transmitted signal paths. Similarly, if the objects around the mobile station are moving at a greater velocity than the mobile station, they also induce a Doppler shift on the multipath components and affect small-scale fading. In case of an aircraft the channel is expected to be static. The effect of Doppler spread due to movement of transmitters, receivers and the surrounding objects need not be considered because transmitters,

receivers and the surrounding objects in an aircraft are static in nature, except in cabin area where there may be slight movement of passengers.

Small scale fading in any wireless channel therefore can be characterized as shown in Fig. 2 based on Time or Doppler spread. Fast fading and slow fading cases due to doppler spread are not considered for aircraft. In case of time spread signals, multipath propagation is caused due to the delay spread. In an aircraft, due to presence of metallic objects, large multipath signals are formed. The fading due to multipath signals is likely to have a Rayleigh distribution, when there is no LOS signal component. The majority of signals in aircraft are likely to follow Rayleigh fading because the LRUs are distributed in different sections, separated by metallic walls. In certain cases, communication may have a LOS component, as in the case of avionics' LRUs mounted in the avionics bay or communication between sensors and gateway in the LG wheel bay. The fading in such a scenario will be Rician if the multiple paths have a strong LOS signal component (Sklar, 1999).

Fig. 2 Factors which affect small scale fading

Fast fading and slow fading cases due to doppler spread are not considered for aircraft. In case of time spread signals, multipath propagation is caused due to the delay spread. In an aircraft, due to the presence of metallic objects, large multipath signals are formed. The fading due to multipath signals is likely to have a Rayleigh distribution, when there is no LOS signal component. The majority of the signals in aircraft are likely to follow Rayleigh fading because the LRUs are distributed in different sections, separated by metallic walls. In certain cases, communication may have a LOS component, as in the case of avionic LRUs mounted in the avionics bay or communication between sensors and gateway in the LG wheel bay. The fading in such a scenario will be Rician if the multiple paths have a strong LOS signal component (Sklar, 1999).

III. Display System Wireless Architecture

This section is pertaining to the proposed wired wireless hybrid architecture for the display system. The proposed architecture is shown in Figure 3. The data path includes wireless sensor transmitting the sensor data, using a predefined wireless protocol, to a data concentrator (PMU), which aggregates the sensor data. The sensors may include pressure, temperature sensors, video sensors, infra-red sensors, radar, weapons etc. The data from PMU is transmitted on a wireless channel to both the IAC. For flight safety critical systems, the medium between the data concentrator and IAC is recommended to have dissimilar redundancy (both wired and wireless) to ensure that flight critical information from system computers like Full Authority Digital Engine Control (FADEC), auto pilot computer, fuel computer etc. is available at the IAC even in case of failure of wireless/wired link. However, the video images from sensors are directly transferred on wireless channel to Display Control Module. These videos are overlaid over the data received at Display Control Module from IAC. This is the concept used in modern military aircraft, including fighters and transport aircraft. This prevents overloading of IAC with video images.

For non-critical systems, data concentrators providing information from smoke sensors, cabin images, aircraft cabin lighting, temperature sensors etc. may have a single wireless channel and redundancy is not required. The two IACs share the data on a wired bus due to the co-location of the units. The IACs and the Display Control Modules are also connected on wireless channel for transfer of information between the two LRUs. Further the data to the cockpit displays is proposed to be on wired network due to smaller distances involved between the Display Control Modules and displays. In case, the distances involved between the two are larger and redundancy in displays is available wireless communication can be considered.

Fig. 3 Proposed Wireless Display System Architecture

A Channel Model for Military Transport Aircraft

The study of available literature has revealed that one of the best known channel model to describe the arrival of Multipath Components (MPCs) due to reflections from objects near transmitters and receivers is the statistical Saleh-Valenzuela (S-V) (Saleh & Valenzuela, February 1987). The model is presented for a middle-sized building at a frequency of 1.5 GHz signal, modulated by a sequence of pulses of 10 ns with 600 ns repetition period. The SV channel model, based on measured values for LOS in a C-130 aircraft, a military transport aircraft, residential area, indoor office and building (same floor) is given in Table 2 and simulation of the cluster and ray decay times of S-V channel model in C-130 aircraft is shown in Figures 4 and 5 respectively.

Table 2 Path Loss Exponents in aircraft and buildings

	γ (ns)	$1/\lambda$ (ns)	Γ (ns)	$1/\Lambda$ (ns)
C-130 (Spiliotopoulos & Kanatas, 2010)	31.02	0.1333	12.89	6.02
Residential area (Molisch, et al.)	12.53	0.65	22.69	21.28
Indoor office (Molisch, et al.)	6.4	5.27	14.6	62.5
Building (Saleh & Valenzuela, February 1987)	20	10	60	200

Fig. 4 Cluster decay time for C-130 aircraft

Fig. 5 Ray decay time for C-130 aircraft

The measurements in the military transport aircraft have brought out the presence of 7-14 clusters (Spiliotopoulos & Kanatas, 2010) as compared to 2 clusters inside a building on the

same floor (Saleh & Valenzuela, February 1987) , 3-4 clusters in residential area (Molisch, et al.) and 5 clusters in indoor office environment (Tentative Criteria for Comparison of Modulation Methods, 1997). The presence of a greater number of clusters is possibly due to the presence of large amount of metallic structure inside the aircraft compared to other indoor environments. Fig. 2 shows the exponential decay of the mean cluster power and exponential decay of the ray power within the cluster is shown in Fig. 3. The plot is compared with the ideal Poisson distribution curve. The simulation has been carried out for 7 clusters and assuming that there are 8 rays in a cluster. The figures show that the clusters go down after ~42 ns and in a cluster the rays die down after ~1 ns. Delay spread measurements inside A 319, DC-3, King Air, Cessna and Piper aircraft, is given in (Schmidt, et al., 2008), (Matolak & Chandrasekaran, 2008) and is tabulated in Table 3 . Though these aircraft are not specifically used for military purposes, the values give an idea of the delay spreads inside aircraft. The RMS delay spread is found to be in line with the measurements inside C-130 (military aircraft) given in Table 2.

Table 3 RMS Delay Spread

Aircraft	Min (ns)	Max (ns)	Mean(ns)
A 319	10	30	26
DC-3	9.5	40	26.3
King Air	9.2	35	23.7
Cessna	14.3	32	24.2
Piper	8.8	45	29.1

B. ITU Recommended Channel Model

The model defined by ITU, based on measurements inside a DC-10 aircraft is more comprehensive. The division of aircraft into six different sections, based on measurements is given in Table 3. The gain/loss model between transmitter and receiver defined by ITU, inside an aircraft by considering large scale and small scale gain/loss model, is of the form (International Telecommunication Union, 2014).

$$L(dB) = h(dB)(f, d) + Y(dB) + X(dB) \quad (4)$$

The large scale channel gain loss model is expected to be of the form

$$h(f, d) = C_1 d^{-n} f^{-k} \tag{5}$$

The values of $C_{1,dB}$, k and n for different groups to reduce the error between the measurement and the model is given in Table 4.

Table 4 Channel parameter values for different groups

Gp	Group name	k (freq exp)	n (dist exp)	$C_{1,dB}$
A	Intra-Cabin & Intra-Flight Deck	2.45	2	189.8
B	Inter-Cabin	2.09	3.46	167.5
C	Inter-Cabin-to-Lower Lobe & Inter-Cabin-to-Flight Deck	1.86	2.49	124.5
D	Inter-Cabin-to-Exterior (points on wing)	1.86	2.12	118.2
E	Inter-Cabin-to-Landing Gear & Inter Lower-Lobe to Exterior	1.59	1.51	77.9
F	Inter-Exterior	1.95	2.31	142.5

The factor Y includes error in $h(f, d)$ model and imperfections in the model itself. The modeling error based on all the measurements was found to be normal with mean $\mu = -0.03 \text{ dB}$. During the propagation modelling measurements, an error may occur due the shadowing effect of the obstacles inside the aircraft. This error in the model Y , in equation (4.16), is observed to have normal distribution with zero mean and $\sigma=4.8 \text{ dB}$ (International Telecommunication Union, 2014).

Fig. 6 Aircraft Path loss Model as per ITU

In case of equation (4), measurements have indicated that the small scale channel gain/loss model X can be modelled as a Rayleigh distribution model with unit variance (International Telecommunication Union, 2014). The path loss model for the six sections based on equation (4) is shown in Figure 6.

C. Channel Model for Flight Deck Display System

The channel model for the display system is based on the location of the sensors and LRUs in the aircraft. The sensors can be located at different locations inside the aircraft and also external to the aircraft. External sensors may include temperature sensors, AoA, cameras etc. Cameras for cockpit and cabin crew will be located inside the aircraft. PMU and IAC will be located in the avionics bay and the Display Control Module is likely to be located closer to the cockpit or in the avionics bay.

The small scale fading model, in an aircraft will follow the Rayleigh Channel model or the Rician Channel model depending on the presence or absence of direct ray in the multipath components. The small scale fading model between sensors and PMU, IAC and Display Control Module, will follow Rayleigh model due to likely locations of the units. In a fighter aircraft, IAC and Display Control Module may be co-located and in such a scenario the fading model will follow Rician model. The channel between PMU and IAC also will either be Rician or Rayleigh depending on the location of LRUs inside the aircraft.

The channel model for the display system can be categorized under Group C and D of ITU channel model given in Table 3. The large scale path loss model for the two groups based on equation (5) is shown in Figure 7 and the channel path loss model based on equation (4) (for Group C and D) is shown in Figure 8. The figures shows that the LRUs of display system should not be placed beyond 20 m to keep the path loss below 90 dB. ITU has also recommended a maximum separation of 15m between two communicating units.

Fig. 7 Large Scale Path Loss model for Group C and D

Fig.8 Channel Path Loss model for Group C and D

IV. Conclusion

With multiple issues related to wirings inside an aircraft, WAIC is likely to define future aircraft systems. In order to implement wireless systems on-board an aircraft, there is a requirement to analyse the channel inside the aircraft. The paper has attempted to analyse the aspects of channel models inside a military transport aircraft, by using channel inside C-130 and commercial aircraft, which are used as platforms for military transportation, AWACS etc. Different indoor propagation channel models were analysed and simulated. The large scale path loss model inside the aircraft was simulated with the path loss exponent value based on measurements in different aircraft. Study of the indoor models has brought out that the aircraft channel model is more likely to follow the S-V model due to the arrival of rays in clusters. The delay spread of signals due to multipath inside multiple aircraft have been found to be similar to C-130 aircraft. Small scale fading inside the aircraft in majority of the cases is likely to follow Rayleigh fading due to compartmentalization, resulting in NLOS condition. The channel model for display system is likely to fall under Group C and D of the sections identified by ITU. Simulation of channel estimation using LS (with linear and spline interpolation) and MMSE

estimation techniques for a Rayleigh fading channel has brought out that MMSE with DFT is the most suitable estimation technique for estimating the channel for the display system.

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